

(1)

- a ; R' = R'' = Me
- b ; R' = R'' = Et
- c ; R' = Me, R'' = Et
- d ; R' = Et, R'' = Me

2

- a ; R = R' = Me, R''' = CH₂C₆H₅
- b ; R = R' = Me, R''' = (CH₂)₃CH₃
- c ; R = R' = Me, R''' = CH(CH₃)₂
- d ; R = R' = Me, R''' = (CH₂)₅CH₃
- e ; R = R' = Me, R''' = (CH₂)₂C₆H₅
- f ; R' = R'' = Et, R''' = CH₂C₆H₅
- g ; R' = R'' = Et, R''' = (CH₂)₃CH₃
- h ; R' = R'' = Et, R''' = CH(CH₃)₂
- i ; R' = R'' = Et, R''' = (CH₂)₅CH₃
- j ; R' = R'' = Et, R''' = (CH₂)₆H₅

3

- a ; R' = Me, R'' = Me
- b ; R' = Et, R'' = Et

4

- a ; R' = Me, R'' = Me
- b ; R' = Et, R'' = Et

Scheme 1

Synthesis and Anti-inflammatory Activity of some Substituted Tetrazoles

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VARIOUS biological activities are associated with tetrazole derivatives^{1,2}. It was of interest to synthesise tetrazoles incorporating (2,4-dialkoxy-5-ethylphenyl)alkyl moieties and study their biological activities.

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The appropriate aldehydes were converted into nitriles via the formation of oxazolones, ketoacids and oximes. The nitriles on treatment with NaN₃ in DMF in presence of NH₄Cl furnished 5-substituted-tetrazoles³ (1a-d) (Scheme 1). Substituted

benzene propanoic acids were converted into the amides on treating the corresponding propanoyl chlorides with various primary amines which were reacted with PCl_5 to get the imidoyl chlorides.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	M. p. °C
1a	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	112–15
1b	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	60–65
1c	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	102
1d	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	99
2a	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
2b	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
2c	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
2d	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
2e	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
2f	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
2g	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
2h	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
2i	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
2j	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Gummy
3a	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_3\text{N}_5$	83
3b	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_3\text{N}_5$	87
4a	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_3\text{N}_5$	92
4b	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_3\text{N}_5$	97

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

The imidoyl chlorides on treatment with NaN_3 and NaOAc in aqueous acetone yielded 1,5-disubstituted-tetrazoles⁴ (2a–j). Similarly, benzylocyanide was converted to 5-amino-1-benzyltetrazole on treatment with NaN_3 in presence of concentrated H_2SO_4 . It was acylated with various substituted-benzene propanoyl/propenoyl chlorides to get various 1,5-disubstituted-tetrazoles⁵ (3a, b, 4a, b).

The compounds (Table 1) were characterised by their elemental analyses and ir and pmr spectral data.

Anti-inflammatory activity: Compounds 1–4 were tested for their anti-inflammatory activity by acute carrageenan oedema tests in rats by the reported technique⁶. The compounds were orally administered at 100 mg/kg dose to male albino rats (110–140 g) in groups of 5, one hour before the injection of carrageenan solution into the left hind foot, and the volume of the paw was measured after 3 h.

The synthesised compounds showed feeble anti-inflammatory activity (3–24% ; control Ibuprofen, 58%). Among 1*H*-5-substituted-benzyltetrazoles (1a–d), substitution on benzene ring, in general, leads to decrease of activity. Among 1,5-disubstituted-tetrazoles (2a–j), maximum activity was observed in 2b (24%) while in 3a, b no change in activity was observed on substitution.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillary tubes on a Buchi melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were run on a Pye-Unicam spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian T60A spectrometer.

1*H*-5-(2,4-Dialkoxy-5-ethylbenzyl)tetrazoles (1a–d): A mixture of 2,4-dialkoxy-5-ethylbenzyl cyanides (0.22 mol), NaN_3 (0.22 mol) and a pinch

of NH_4Cl taken in DMF (30 ml) was refluxed with continuous stirring at 130° for 17–24 h. DMF was then distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue was put in ice-cold water acidified with HCl. The oil so obtained was purified by column chromatography to get pale coloured solids, m.p.s. 65–100°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 140 (NH), 1 672 (C=N) and 1 309 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl_3) 1.20 (3H, t, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 1.56 (3H, t, OCH_2CH_3), 2.49 (2H, q, ArCH_2CH_2), 3.47 (2H, s, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{-C=N}$), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.82 (1H, s, ArH) and 7.0 (1H, s, ArH).

1-Alkyl-5-[2-(2,4-dialkoxy-5-ethylphenyl)ethyl]-tetrazoles (2a–j): 2,4-Dialkoxy-5-ethylbenzenepropanamides were converted into imidoyl chlorides by heating it with PCl_5 (0.1 mol) at 130° for 2 h till fumes of HCl ceased. Excess of POCl_3 was then removed under reduced pressure. The imidoyl chlorides thus obtained were directly added to an ice-cold solution of NaN_3 and $\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in acetone and the mixture was stirred for 24 h. Acetone was distilled off, the residue after repeated treatment with petroleum ether yielded tetrazoles as light brown low melting solids; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 670 (C=N) and 1 306 cm^{-1} (C–N); δ (CDCl_3) 1.20 (3H, t, ArCH_2CH_3 and $\text{N-CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{CH}_3$), 1.57 (N- $\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{-CH}_3$), 2.49 (4H, m, ($\text{ArCH}_2\text{-CH}_2$ and $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{C=N-}$), 2.91 (2H, t, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{C=N-}$), 3.81 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.91 (2H, q, OCH_2CH_3), 4.1 (2H, s, N- $\text{CH}_2\text{-R}$), 6.61 (1H, s, ArH) and 7.00 (1H, s, ArH).

5-[3-(2,4-Dialkoxy-5-ethylphenyl)propanoylamino]-1-benzyltetrazole (3a–b and 4a–b): A mixture of 2,4-dialkoxy-5-ethylbenzenepropanoyl chloride/propenoyl chlorides and 5-amino-1-benzyltetrazole in dry benzene and DMSO, was refluxed on a water-bath for 36 h, then cooled, treated with water, washed with NaHCO_3 solution and 6% HCl and dried over CaCl_2 . The benzene extract was concentrated and the solids were crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as pale yellow shining solids, m.p. 83–97°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 140 (NH), 2 880 (CH) and 1 672 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl_3) 1.20 (3H, t, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 1.40 (6H, t, $2\times\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.49 (4H, m, ArCH_2CH_3 and ArCH_2CH_2), 3.21 (2H, t, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{C=}$), 3.36 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.99 (2H, q, $\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 4.01 (2H, s, N- CH_2), 4.29 (1H, d, ArCH=CH), 5.56 (1H, d, ArCH=CH), 6.59 (1H, s, ArH), 7.01 (1H, s, ArH) and 7.49 (5H, s, N- $\text{CH}_2\text{-ArH}$).

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